

Results of “**Stress drop and seismic efficiency distributions over the Adriatic indenter (European Southeastern Alps)**” by L. Cataldi, M. Picozzi, M. D’Amico, P. Morasca, D. Bindi, V. Poggi, G. Costa, A. Vigano’, D. Spallarossa, submitted to Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth

The archive contains:

REPO

- | - **GIToutput** [Results of the GIT spectral decomposition](#)
- | | - attenuation.txt --> spectral attenuation (distance, frequencies)
- | | - site_amp.csv --> site amplifications
- | | - sources.csv --> source spectra (frequency, event IDs)
- | | - GIT_sources.jpg --> figure of source spectra
- | | - GIT_sites.jpg --> figure of site amplifications
- | | - GIT_attenuation.jpg --> figure of attenuations
- | - **FITparams** [Results of the source spectra fitting](#)
- | | - table_source_parameters.csv --> table with fitted source parameters
- | - **INFO** [Information about events, stations and velocity model](#)
- | | - events.csv
- | | - stations.csv
- | | - velmodel.txt

Columns of the source parameter tables:

ID: event ID (YYMMGGhhmmss)
ml: local magnitude
mw: moment magnitude
m0, dm0: seismic moment [Nm] and its error
fc, dfc: corner frequency [Hz] and its error
es, des: radiated energy [J] and its error
stdrop, dstdrop: stress drop [Pa] and its error
tau, dtau: apparent stress [Pa] and its error
eta, deta: Savage-Wood efficiency and its error.

Columns of the velocity model table:

NUM: number of the layer
H: starting depth of the layer
VP: P-wave velocity of the layer [km/s]
VS: S-wave velocity of the layer [km/s]
RHO: density [10^3 kg/(m³)].